

Data Management Plan (DMP) for the #ConnectingMinds Project OPINION Lab

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DMP Version	Effective Date	Changes
OPINION Lab_Hoedl_Schoberer_Eglseer_1.0 Zenodo DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5603353	01/18/2022	Initial version sent to FWF
OPINION Lab_Hoedl_Schoberer_Eglseer_2.0 Zenodo DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7656872	02/20/2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New ethical approval: 35-093 ex 22/23: Opinion Lab • Not assessing e.g.Care dependency • Focus on the perspective of the residents • Focus on pain and quality of life • Including internationally agreed-on meta-tool for Pain Assessment in Impaired Cognition
OPINION Lab_Hoedl_Schoberer_Eglseer_3.0 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14747723	01/27/2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New ethical approval: 1371/2024 • Implementation of a pain management toolkit
OPINION Lab_Hoedl_Schoberer_Eglseer_4.0 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18324464	01/21/2026	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prolonging of ethical approval: 1371/2024 • Changes in data collection <p>The changes are marked in blue.</p>

General information	
Project Coordinator and Principal Investigator/ data officer responsible for data management and DMP	PD. Dr. Manuela Hoedl, MSc, BSc; Institute of Nursing Science, Medical University of Graz, orcid.org/0000-0001-9829-2766
Project title and acronym	Open Innovation Nursing Lab (OPINION Lab)
Project abstract	Objectives: The overall project objective is to implement evidence-based nursing care in nursing home practice and improve nursing home care by (1.) establishing an “OPINION lab” in one nursing home; and (2) developing, testing and implementing evidence-based nursing interventions in joint collaboration and partnerships with stakeholders to provide sustainable, evidence-based solutions for problems in this nursing home. Based on the workshop results, the main topics addressed will be dementia and pain. Approach: We will use an approach based on the Living lab methodology. Therefore, one nursing scientist (PhD student) will work in joint collaboration with all stakeholders in the nursing home on one day a week, acting both as intermediary between research and practice and an innovator to develop new nursing care methods. In the first project phase, we will use a mixed method design to address multifaceted questions that arise due to the complexity of the topics dementia and pain and to gain a more holistic picture. These results will help us to identify specific problems, needs, expectations, potentials and resources with regard to dementia and pain care. Supportive, practice-oriented and problem-oriented tools/innovations will then be developed for the respective nursing home practice.
Start and end date of project	01.06.2022-31.05.2027
Funding programme/ grant number	FWF #Connecting Minds programme/CM 300
Medical University of Graz project management ID/ Medical University of Graz project notification ID	10982/ 11305

Relevant policies and guidelines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medical University of Graz “Policy für Forschungsdatenmanagement” • Medical University of Graz “Standards of Good Scientific Practice” • Medical University of Graz “Open Access Policy” • Medical University of Graz “Guidelines for Data Protection and IT Security” • FWF “Berlin Declaration on Open Access to Knowledge in the Sciences and Humanities” • FWF “Core Requirements for Data Management Plans from Science Europe”
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I	Data Characteristics
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I.1	Description of the data	<p>Data type, format, and volume</p> <p>We will use the nursing records and questionnaires to generate quantitative data (in detail see table below). We plan to involve in the whole project at least 100 residents and nursing (management) staff from one nursing home.</p> <p>At the end of the project, all files are stored in formats that are as open and standardized as possible. The file format PDF/A, and CSV as well as rtf are used for this purpose. Where conversion to an open format is not possible, original formats are stored.</p>
	Changes in comparison to DMP Version 3.0	<p>In a workshop in June 2023, nursing staff, scientists, nursing managers, managers of the organization decided to develop a toolkit with non-pharmacological interventions for pain management in nursing homes. Between June 2023 and June 2024, the toolbox was developed and is freely available:</p> <p>https://pflugwissenschaft.medunigraz.at/frontend/user_upload/OEs/institute/pflugwissenschaft/pdf/Werkzeugkoffer_Opinion_Lab_OPINION_LAB_de_v03.pdf</p> <p>In the next step we plan to implement and evaluate the toolbox in the nursing home. In the process of preparing the implementation, we found that the Barthel-Index was not available and not used anymore by the nursing home staff. Due to the fact, that we wanted to hold the workload for the staff as low as possible, we decided not to collect data regarding the Activities of daily living with the Barthel-Index anymore. The other change was, that we used the „Beurteilung von “Schmerzen bei Demenz (BESD)” instead of the planned ECPA. This was done, because it was already used by the nursing home staff.</p>

Quantitative Data									
Investigation	Data Source	Method	Measurement instrument	Data type	Data file format		Processing software	File location	Estimated data volume
					Raw	Analyzed			
Demographics	Nursing records	Questionnaire	Nursing records	Numbers	.sav	.sav	SPSS	Drive P:/OPINION Lab_CM 300	0,5 GB
Medical Diagnosis									
Care level									
Non-pharmacological interventions									
Pain medication									
Frequency of pain									
Pain intensity									
Pain impairment	Residents		NRS/BESD						
			PEG Scale						
Demographics	Staff	Online Survey	Questionnaire						
Qualification									
Workplace									
Self-efficacy in pain management			Scale Brunkert						
Implementation barriers/facilitators			pCAT + 5 ERIC						
Appropriateness of the toolbox			IAM						
Feasibility of the toolbox			FIM						
Penetration of the toolbox	Nursing records	Calculation	Nursing records					0,5 GB	

II Documentation and Metadata		
II.1	Metadata standards	We plan to use international recommended standards such as ICD 10 as meta standards for medical diagnosis. Pain frequency and intensity are recommended internationally as core outcome set, when studying pain (Bova et al., 2023). The PEG scale was chosen, as this scale is recommended to measure pain impairment as a common data element (Wandner et al., 2022).
II.2	Documentation of data	<p>We plan to involve in the whole project about 100 residents and staff from one nursing home.</p> <p>Due to the fact, that only one nursing home participates during the whole project, we cannot guarantee that the data are anonymized in a way, that the personal of the rights and freedoms of data subjects are assured. As an example:</p> <p>We assume that 80 residents participate. Even if we follow the anonymization process by using e.g. 'suppression', 'banding/generalization', 'perturbation' or 'data swapping', depending on the variables according to the "Guidelines for data anonymization report" of OPERANDO (H2020 – 653704) a project of the European commission, it is highly probable, that less than five residents are e.g. almost care independent. In combination with the fact, that only one nursing home is participating, there is a high chance of re-identification of the data subjects. This is specifically problematic, as we collect highly sensitive data on the residents such as medical diagnosis.</p> <p>Moreover, based on the fact that only one nursing home is participating in this project, there is even a chance that only a few staff members participate, which leads us to the decision not to publish our data.</p>
II.3	Data quality control	In order to ensure the integrity and quality of the research data and increase the potential for data sharing, at least two project members will check randomly assigned 10% of the collected data.

III Data Availability and Storage		
III.1	Data sharing strategy	<p>Regarding data sharing during the research project:</p> <p>Off-campus access for the employees of the Medical University of Graz is via the Citrix portal or the Nextcloud of the Medical University of Graz. Any sensitive data that needs to be transmitted electronically will be transmitted pseudonymized by using the ACOnet file sender of the Medical University of Graz.</p>
III.2	Data storage strategy	<p>The research data underlying the publication, but also other relevant milestone versions of the project files are archived for at least ten years. During the project we will make use of network drive-P [Project] and the Medical University of Graz Nextcloud for storage and sharing of our research data – both ensuring automatic daily back-up.</p> <p>The expected total size of the remaining data is about 100 GB. The project results and all relevant research data will be stored for at least ten years at servers of Medical University of Graz using the backup service of the university, with no additional costs. No technical barriers.</p> <p>The data management plan will be reviewed at each annual meeting during the life of the project to ensure the success of our long-term data handling strategy.</p>

IV		Legal and Ethical Aspects
IV.1	Legal aspects	<p>There are no legal barriers in making the research data accessible. However, due to the fact that the personal data in our project cannot be anonymized, our data cannot be made publically available</p> <p>Medical University of Graz is entitled to exercise the unrestricted right to use data generated on behalf of or in the interest of Medical University of Graz. The authors or inventors retain the legally reserved right to be named, the right of university staff to independently publish scientific work and the right to be named as a (co-)author in the publication of research results.</p> <p>Articles are published as open access and therefore visible to all researchers and the public.</p>
IV.2	Ethical aspects	<p>Once a participant has given his/her informed consent to participation and data collection, the investigator will assign the participants a unique patient identification code. Therefore, data will be recorded in pseudonymized form using exclusively participants' identification code. The participants' identification code list (O:\wv\i-pflwis\w-alle\FP_Opinion_Lab) will remain separated from the participants' datasets (Drive P:/OPINION Lab_CM 300). The observational participation has been approved by the ethical committee of Medical University of Graz, (Number: 34-074 ex 21/22: Opinon Lab). and written informed consent will be obtained from all study participants.</p> <p>The ethical committee of the Medical University also approved the study protocol, focusing on demographics, cognitive status, pain prevalence/intensity/Interventions as well on quality of life and research participation for the second study. (Number: 35-093 ex 22/23: Opinon Lab).</p> <p>The ethical committee of the Medical University also approved and prolonged the study protocol, focusing on the residents and staff as described in the data characteristics (Number: 1371/2024).</p>